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**ANALYSIS OF TERMINOLOGY USED IN ORAL
POTENTIALLY MALIGNANT DISORDERS: A
BIBLIOMETRIC STUDY OF TRENDS IN THE 100 MOST
CITED ARTICLES (2007–2024)**

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**Analysis of Terminology Used in Oral Potentially
Malignant Disorders: A Bibliometric Study of Trends in
the 100 Most Cited Articles (2007–2024)**

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ABSTRACT

Objective: To perform a bibliometric analysis of the 100 most-cited articles on oral potentially malignant disorders (OPMD), focusing on the adoption and evolution of terminology from 2007 to 2024.

Materials and Methods: A comprehensive bibliometric search was conducted using the Web of Science database, following PRIBA guidelines. After applying eligibility criteria, the 100 most-cited articles were selected. Statistical and network analyses were used to evaluate terminology trends and collaborative patterns.

Results: The term OPMD, introduced by the WHO Collaborating Centre for Oral Cancer in 2007, was widely adopted among the top 100 articles, though 60 continued using non-standardized or hybrid terminology. The most frequently associated keywords were OPMD and Oral Premalignant Lesion. A clear trend toward increased use of OPMD over time was observed. Articles with non-standardized keywords were predominantly authored by researchers from Asia and North America, while institutions in the UK showed a stronger preference for the standardized term.

Conclusions: While the term OPMD has gained broader acceptance, the use of non-standardized terminology remains. This study highlights the need for consistent terminology, advocating for the adoption of OPMD to enhance research coherence and facilitate interdisciplinary understanding.

1. INTRODUCTION

The terminology used for oral lesions and conditions that may progress to oral squamous cell carcinoma (OSCC) has varied over the years. In 2005, a consensus of a working group coordinated by the WHO Collaborating Centre for Oral Cancer introduced the term oral potentially malignant disorders (OPMD) (Warnakulasuriya, Johnson & van der Waal, 2007), which was later adopted by the 2017 Classification of Head and Neck Tumors (WHO, 2017) and by the recently published IARC/WHO Handbook for Oral Cancer Prevention (Reibel et al., 2017; IARC, 2023). OPMD refers to a heterogeneous and complex group of 11 oral mucosal disorders whose clinical presentation may precede the transformation into OSCC (Warnakulasuriya, 2018).

The term OPMD was proposed as a replacement for the commonly used terms "pre-malignant" and "pre-cancerous" oral lesions because it more accurately reflects the natural history of these precursor lesions and conditions. The terms "pre-malignant" and "pre-cancerous" may misleadingly suggest that any given lesion will inevitably progress to malignancy, while the risk is only statistically elevated (Speight, Khurram & Kujan, 2018). Therefore, the term "potentially malignant," which indicates that progression to malignancy is merely a possibility, was proposed and has gained wider acceptance. Another issue was the differentiation between potentially malignant "lesions" and "conditions." To address this, the 2007 WHO workshop recommended abandoning this distinction in favor of the unified term "disorders" (Warnakulasuriya, 2018), as initially suggested in the 1977 WHO classification (Warnakulasuriya, Johnson & van der Waal, 2007).

The use of the term OPMD not only reflects the variation in the risk of malignant transformation of the oral mucosa at sites with clinically visible changes, but also considers that any part of the lining mucosa of the oral cavity could carry the risk for OSCC development due to field change (Warnakulasuriya, Johnson & van der Waal, 2007), usually due to exposure to environmental carcinogens (Warnakulasuriya et al., 2018). Adopting the term OPMD helps clarify the future clinical behavior of these disorders for nonexperts and lay persons and aids in understanding their nature. Additionally, the standardization of terminology in the scientific literature has significance in epidemiology and clinical studies (Warnakulasuriya, Johnson & van der Waal, 2007).

Bibliometric analysis combines quantitative and qualitative methods to examine scientific literature by analyzing the external characteristics of all publications on a

specific topic. This approach uses systematic statistical, mathematical, and review processes to assess the current research status, trends, and characteristics of a given subject from both performance and network perspectives. Performance analysis evaluates research productivity based on the number of citations and rankings, while network analysis uncovers scientific connections through co-authorship and co-citation analysis (Koo & Lin, 2023). Additionally, bibliometric analysis can examine the types of articles, primary scientific methods used in a field, and their implications for research (Gueiros et al., 2024). These analyses can be conducted at multiple levels, including individual authors, journals, institutions, and geographical regions, thereby providing key bibliometric indicators (Koo & Lin, 2023). This methodology has been used to investigate trends in publications related to OPMD (Gueiros et al., 2024; Gondivkar et al., 2018; Liu et al., 2020; Foy et al., 2018); but none of the studies have specifically explored the terminology used for OPMD.

Efforts are underway to standardize terminology on training platforms, such as the OPMD Healthcare Professional Training by an European consortium of experts co-funded by the Erasmus+ program of the European Union, particularly discussing the challenges faced during the translation of the OPMD term into European languages like Portuguese, Spanish, Italian, and French (Monteiro et al., 2023).

Despite the adoption of the term OPMD by the WHO, there is still significant variation in the terminology used by the authors in English-language articles, leading to confusion and misunderstandings. Therefore, this study conducted a bibliometric analysis to identify the terms used to describe OPMD in the 100 most cited articles on OPMD and oral cancer published in English between 2017 and 2024 and to analyze the contexts in which these terms are employed.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Data source

This study's report followed the Preferred Reporting Items for Bibliometric Analysis (PRIBA) guidelines (Koo & Lin, 2023) (**APPENDIX 1**). A bibliometric search was conducted using the Clarivate Analytics Web of Science (WoS) database (<http://www.webofknowledge.com>) to gather citation information on published articles related to OPMD. The search covered the period from 2007 to 2024, corresponding to

the WHO Collaborating Centre’s proposal in 2005 (published in 2007) (Warnakulasuriya, Johnson & van der Waal, 2007) and WHO’s adoption of the term OPMD in its 2017 Classification of Head and Neck Tumors (Reibel et al., 2017). The search was performed on December 6th, 2024, with no restrictions on the language of the studies. A detailed electronic search strategy, including specific word combinations and truncations, was developed for the WoS database. This strategy incorporated both current and past terms used as synonyms for OPMD, as well as the names of lesions or conditions classified as OPMD by the WHO in 2017 (**Table 1**).

Table 1. Primary research topics covered by the 100 most cited articles on OPMD.

Study Topic	Total Studies
Malignant transformation	17
Miscellaneous	15
Management	13
Diagnosis	10
Prognostic Biomarkers	8
Salivary biomarkers	7
Screening	5
Pathogenesis/Etiology	6
Epidemiology	6
Risk factors	4
Clinical features	3
Nomenclature	2
Histological features	2
Microbiological profile	2

Eligibility criteria

Articles eligible for this bibliometric analysis included clinical trials, cohort studies, case-control studies, cross-sectional studies, in vitro or ex vivo (laboratory) studies, case studies (case series and single case reports), systematic reviews, narrative reviews, bibliometric analyses, and editorials focusing primarily on OPMD. The analysis included

studies that used any of the following related terms: OPMD, premalignant oral lesion, oral premalignant disorder, oral premalignancy, and precursor lesion. To simplify the pooled word cloud analysis, any plural forms of these terms were converted to singular.

Studies were excluded from this analysis if they met any of the following criteria: 1) Articles addressing a lesion classified as OPMD, but without any mention, discussion, or use of OPMD-related terms or their synonyms for oral premalignant lesions; 2) Articles published in 2007 but accepted in previous years, prior to the adoption of the term OPMD; 3) Studies mentioning precursor or premalignant lesions in regions of the body other than the mouth; 4) Conference abstracts.

Selection process

Three authors (B.S.F.S., L.V.S.T.V., and F.P.Y.S.) independently reviewed the references downloaded from the WoS database and selected the 100 most cited articles that met the eligibility criteria. The articles were ranked in descending order based on the number of citations. The selection process occurred in two phases. In phase 1, two authors (B.S.F.S. and L.V.S.T.V.) independently assessed the titles and abstracts of the articles, applying the eligibility criteria. If consensus could not be reached, a third author (F.P.Y.S.) made the final decision. In phase 2, the full text of the selected articles was blindly reviewed by the same two authors from phase 1 to ensure correct application of the eligibility criteria. The same strategy used in phase 1 was followed if consensus was not reached. The Rayyan software (Qatar Computing Research Institute) was used to manage the references and ensure a blinded selection process (Ouzzani et al., 2016). The final list of the 100 most cited articles on OPMD was ranked in descending order by the citation count.

Data extraction

To provide the bibliometric indicators for this analysis, two independent authors (B.S.F.S. and F.P.Y.S.) recorded the following information: number of citations, specialty of the first author, country of origin of the first author, complete authorship of the article, publication title, publication year, journal name, journal category, study design, study topic (theme), keywords related to OPMD, and institutional affiliation. The author's specialty was determined based on their professional practice as stated in the article or the official institutional website. If this information was not available in the article or on the institutional homepage, the authors' profiles were reviewed on Google Scholar and/or ResearchGate. The author's country was identified by their institutional affiliation. The

journal category was determined based on the primary area of interest specified in the WoS database. If this information was not available in the database, the journal's official homepage was assessed. The studies were categorized according to their design (cohort study, cross-sectional study, case series, case report, editorial, systematic review, narrative review, bibliometric analysis, and laboratory study), and their themes - study topics (Nomenclature, Molecular profile, Risk factors, Malignant transformation, Epidemiology, Clinical features, Management, Screening, Diagnosis, Microbiological profile, Metabolic profile, Histological features, Immunological profile, Salivary biomarkers, Prognostic biomarkers, Quality of life, and Miscellaneous). Due to the inclusion of narrative reviews, some studies were classified under more than one theme. If a study addressed more than two main topics, it was classified as miscellaneous. The use of former terminology related to OPMD in the article's keywords section was excluded from data extraction, as it may have been used solely for indexing purposes.

Data analysis

Descriptive statistics were performed using Excel software (Microsoft Corporation. Microsoft Excel. Version 16.0, Microsoft, 2018) to summarize key bibliometric indicators. The analysis included the distribution of the most cited publications from 2007 to 2024 that used the term OPMD, the main research topics covered, the predominant study designs (e.g., clinical trials, cohort studies, systematic reviews), and the number of articles per country of affiliation, providing perceptions into global research productivity on OPMD. Additionally, the analysis focused on identifying the most frequently studied OPMD lesions or conditions, examining the association between the authors' specialties and the specific keywords they adopted referring to OPMD (e.g., premalignant oral lesions, oral precancerous lesions). The use of non-standardized, outdated, or hybrid terminology was evaluated in each article. Its usage was categorized into one of three groups: "Discussing the transition to OPMD terminology", "Reflecting the terminology used in referenced studies", or "Other contexts", when the use did not align with the first two classifications.

Data were exported from the Web of Science (WoS) database in text format and then imported into RStudio (RStudio Team, 2024) for preprocessing. The dataset underwent extensive cleaning to correct errors, resolve spelling inconsistencies, and address terminology discrepancies, thereby ensuring its integrity and consistency. This preprocessing was conducted using R and the Bibliometrix package (Aria & Cuccurullo, 2017), which offers robust tools for bibliometric analysis. The Biblioshiny interface was

employed to perform both quantitative and qualitative graphical analyses. Additionally, the overall frequency of studies utilizing the term "OPMD" was calculated, providing perceptions into the term's adoption since its introduction by the WHO Collaborating Centre for Oral Cancer in 2007 and its subsequent endorsement by the WHO in 2017 (Reibel et al., 2017).

The relationship between authors' institutional affiliations and the keywords used in their studies was analyzed to identify geographic and institutional trends in the adoption of specific keywords. Graphs were created to illustrate the evolution of these keywords over time, providing insights into their temporal trends from 2007 to 2017 (prior to their adoption by the WHO) and from 2017 to 2024 (after their adoption by the WHO) (van Eck NJ, Waltman, 2010). The occurrence of OPMD-related keywords over time was also graphically represented and evaluated. Citation analysis was conducted to measure the citation impact of individual studies, authors, and journals, enabling the identification of the most influential works and research outputs in the field. A clustering by coupling analysis was performed to visualize relationships between authors based on their keyword usage. This analysis used authors as the unit of analysis, with coupling determined by shared keywords. The impact was assessed using global citation scores, and clusters were labeled using the keyword-plus method. The walktrap algorithm was applied for clustering, facilitating the identification of thematic connections and research communities within the field of OPMD.

3. RESULTS

The bibliometric search identified 11,836 references related to OPMD, based on this study's eligibility criteria and limited to publications from 2007 to 2024. From these, the top 500 most cited references were selected for analysis. In this process, 351 were excluded because they were conference abstracts, did not mention any terms related to OPMD, or were accepted for publication before 2007, prior to the WHO's Collaborating Centre for Oral Cancer adoption of the term OPMD. A flowchart of the selection process is available in **Figure 1**.

Figure 1. Flowchart illustrating the literature search process, adapted from the PRISMA guidelines.

The selection process then proceeded in two phases to identify the 100 most cited articles published in English. The primary research topics covered by the selected articles were Malignant transformation, Miscellaneous, Management, Diagnosis, Salivary biomarkers, and Prognostic Biomarkers. The remaining publications addressed other topics or various combinations of these major topics (**Table 1**). Most of the selected publications were narrative reviews, systematic reviews, or cross-sectional studies.

Figure 2 provides detailed information about the study designs of the 100 selected publications. The main published topic among OPMD was oral lichen planus. The United Kingdom was the most prolific country in terms of the number of top 100 articles, with 23 articles. The complete distribution of articles by country of affiliation shown in **Figure 3**.

Figure 2. Study design distribution of the 100 selected publications.

Figure 3. Distribution of articles by country of affiliation.

The citation counts for the 100 most-cited articles ranged from 969 to 91 based on the WoS Core Collection's Times Cited metric, and from 1,100 to 108 based on the Total Times Cited metric. The most-cited publication, published in 2007, focused on the nomenclature and classification of OPMD as defined by the WHO Collaborating Centre for Oral Cancer (**Table 2**) (Warnakulasuriya, Johnson & van der Waal, 2007). Among the most-cited articles on OPMD published between 2007 and 2024, the majority (52.5%) were in 2009 (n=12), 2011 (n=9), and 2016 (n=9). The next group, accounting for 20%, was focused on 2007 (n=9) and 2018 (n=5). Articles from 2014 (n=8) and 2015 (n=6) made up 17.5%. The remaining years contributed to the final 10% of the most-cited articles (Table 2). Overall, 74% of the most-cited articles were published between 2007 and 2016, while 26% were published between 2017 and 2024.

The highest number of cited articles appeared in Oral Diseases (n=13), Journal of Oral Pathology & Medicine (n=12), Oral Oncology (n=12), and Oral Surgery, Oral Medicine, Oral Pathology, Oral Radiology (n=10), with most journals focusing on Oral Medicine and Oral Pathology (**Table 3**). In terms of author specialties, the majority of first authors specialize in Oral Medicine (n=31) or Oral Pathology (n=25), or both (n=5). Few authors represent general medical fields (**Table 4**).

Table 2. Top 100 most cited articles included in the bibliometric analysis and the terminology used in Oral Potentially Malignant Disorders.

Rank	Authors	Title	WoS Core Collection Times Cited Count	Total Times Cited Count*	Journal	Year	Journal's Specialty	Study Type	Term Adopted
1	Warnakulasuriya, S; Johnson, NW; Van der Waal, I	Nomenclature and classification of potentially malignant disorders of the oral mucosa	969	1100	J. Oral Pathol. Med.	2007	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine; Pathology	Narrative review	Potentially malignant disorder; pre-cancer; precursor lesion; premalignant; intra epithelial neoplasia
2	Chi, AC; Day, TA; Neville, BW	Oral cavity and oropharyngeal squamous cell carcinomaan update	770	834	CA-Cancer J. Clin.	2015	Oncology	Narrative review	Potentially malignant disorder
3	Vigneswaran, N; Williams, MD	Epidemiologic Trends in Head and Neck Cancer and Aids in Diagnosis	574	644	Oral Maxillofac. Surg. Clin. N. Am.	2014	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Narrative review	Potentially malignant disorders; precancer; precancerous changes; precursor lesion; premalignant lesion; premalignant condition;
4	Rivera, C	Essentials of oral cancer	568	628	Int. J. Clin. Exp. Pathol.	2015	Oncology; Pathology	Narrative review	Potentially malignant disorder; oral potentially malignant disorder; epithelial precursor lesion; malignant disorders; oral precancer
5	Konopka, K; Goslinski, T	Photodynamic therapy in dentistry	565	619	J. Dent. Res.	2007	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Narrative review	Precancerous lesion; premalignant lesion of the oral mucosa; mucosal premalignant lesion
6	van der Waal, I	Potentially malignant disorders of the oral and oropharyngeal mucosa; terminology, classification and present concepts of management	551	621	Oral Oncol.	2009	Oncology; Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Narrative review	Potentially malignant disorder of the oral mucosa; potentially malignant lesion; potentially malignant condition; potentially malignant disorder; premalignant; precancerous

7	Warnakulasuriya, S; Kujan, O; Aguirre-Urizar, JM; Bagan, JV; González-Moles, MA; Kerr, AR; Lodi, G; Mello, FW; Monteiro, L; Ogden, GR; Sloan, P; Johnson, NW	Oral potentially malignant disorders: A consensus report from an international seminar on nomenclature and classification, convened by the WHO Collaborating Centre for Oral Cancer	501	526	Oral Dis.	2021	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Narrative review	Oral potentially malignant disorder; potentially malignant disorder; potentially malignant disorder of the oral mucosa; precancer, epithelial precursor lesions; premalignant; precancerous; intra-epithelial lesion; potentially premalignant oral epithelial lesion; premalignancy
8	Warnakulasuriya, S; Reibel, J; Bouquot, J; Dabelsteen, E	Oral epithelial dysplasia classification systems: predictive value, utility, weaknesses and scope for improvement	422	482	J. Oral Pathol. Med.	2008	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine; Pathology	Narrative review	Potentially malignant disorder of the oral cavity; Potentially malignant disorder; potentially malignant lesion; potentially malignant oral lesion; precancer; precursor lesion
9	Sridharan, G; Ramani, P; Patankar, S; Vijayaraghavan, R	Evaluation of salivary metabolomics in oral leukoplakia and oral squamous cell carcinoma	378	399	J. Oral Pathol. Med.	2019	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine; Pathology	Case-control study	Oral potentially malignant disorderpotentially malignant disorder
10	Napier, SS; Speight, PM	Natural history of potentially malignant oral lesions and conditions: an overview of the literature	372	435	J. Oral Pathol. Med.	2008	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine; Pathology	Narrative review	Potentially malignant disorder; potentially malignant lesion; potentially malignant condition; potentially malignant oral lesion; potentially malignant oral condition
11	Roopashree, MR; Gondhalekar, RV; Shashikanth, MC; George, J; Thippeswamy, SH; Shukla, A	Pathogenesis of oral lichen planus - a review	344	372	J. Oral Pathol. Med.	2010	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine; Pathology	Narrative review	Premalignant condition
12	Al-Hashimi, I; Schifter, M; Lockhart, PB; Wray, D; Brennan, M; Migliorati, CA; Axéll, T; Bruce, AJ; Carpenter, W; Eisenberg, E; Epstein, JB; Holmstrup,	Oral lichen planus and oral lichenoid lesions:: diagnostic and therapeutic considerations	342	371	Oral Surg. Oral Med. Oral Pathol. Oral Radiol. Endod.	2007	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Narrative review	Precancerous; premalignant

	P; Jontell, M; Lozada-Nur, F; Nair, R; Silverman, B; Thongprasom, K; Thornhill, M; Warnakulasuriya, S; van der Waal, I								
13	Kumar, M; Nanavati, R; Modi, TG; Dobariya, C	Oral cancer: Etiology and risk factors: A review	323	351	J. Canc. Res. Ther.	2016	Oncology	Narrative review	Oral precancer; oral premalignant lesions
14	Speight, PM; Khurram, SA; Kujan, O	Oral potentially malignant disorders: risk of progression to malignancy	314	345	Oral Surg. Oral Med. Oral Pathol. Oral Radiol.	2018	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Narrative review	Oral potentially malignant disorder; potentially malignant disorder; precancerous lesion; premalignant lesion; potentially premalignant
15	Cheng, YSL; Gould, A; Kurago, Z; Fantasia, J; Muller, S	Diagnosis of oral lichen planus: a position paper of the American Academy of Oral and Maxillofacial Pathology	312	335	Oral Surg. Oral Med. Oral Pathol. Oral Radiol.	2016	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Narrative review	Precancerous condition; oral precancerous lesion; premalignant; premalignant oral lesion; premalignant condition
16	Warnakulasuriya, S; Ariyawardana, A	Malignant transformation of oral leukoplakia: a systematic review of observational studies	282	311	J. Oral Pathol. Med.	2016	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine; Pathology	Systematic review	Oral potentially indignant disorder; potentially malignant disorder; oral mucosal disorder; precancerous; premalignant
17	Warnakulasuriya, S; Fennell, N; Diz, P; Seoane, J; Rapidis, A	An appraisal of oral cancer and pre-cancer screening programmes in Europe: a systematic review	282	311	J. Oral Pathol. Med.	2015	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine; Pathology	Systematic review	Potentially malignant disorder; oral potentially malignant disorder; potentially cancerous; potentially malignant lesion; precancer; pre-cancerous
18	Alrashdan, MS; Cirillo, N; McCullough, M	Oral lichen planus: a literature review and update	280	311	Arch. Dermatol. Res.	2016	Dermatology	Narrative review	Potentially malignant

19	Mehanna, HM; Rattay, T; Smith, J; McConkey, CC	TREATMENT AND FOLLOW-UP OF ORAL DYSPLASIA - A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW AND META-ANALYSIS	278	299	Head Neck-J. Sci. Spec. Head Neck	2009	Otorhinolaryngology; Surgery	Systematic review	Premalignant condition
20	Kademani, D	Oral cancer	275	305	Mayo Clin. Proc.	2007	Medicine, General & Internal	Narrative review	Premalignant lesion; premalignant oral lesion; premalignant condition
21	Iocca, O; Sollecito, TP; Alawi, F; Weinstein, GS; Newman, JG; De Virgilio, A; Di Maio, P; Spriano, G; López, SP; Shanti, RM	Potentially malignant disorders of the oral cavity and oral dysplasia: A systematic review and meta-analysis of malignant transformation rate by subtype	265	280	Head Neck-J. Sci. Spec. Head Neck	2020	Otorhinolaryngology; Surgery	Systematic review	Potentially malignant disorder of the oral cavity
22	Chaw, SY; Majeed, AA; Dalley, AJ; Chan, A; Stein, S; Farah, CS	Epithelial to mesenchymal transition (EMT) biomarkers - E-cadherin, beta-catenin, APC and Vimentin - in oral squamous cell carcinogenesis and transformation	236	270	Oral Oncol.	2012	Oncology; Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Cross-sectional study	Potentially malignant oral lesion; potentially malignant lesion; precancerous
23	Syrjänen, S; Lodi, G; von Bültzingslöwen, I; Aliko, A; Arduino, P; Campisi, G; Challacombe, S; Ficarra, G; Flaitz, C; Zhou, HM; Maeda, H; Miller, C; Jontell, M	Human papillomaviruses in oral carcinoma and oral potentially malignant disorders: a systematic review	235	262	Oral Dis.	2011	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Systematic review	Oral potentially malignant disorder; oral precancer; oral precancerous lesion; oral precancerous condition; premalignant lesion; premalignant lesion; premalignant oral lesion; premalignant condition;
24	Gonzalez-Moles, MA; Scully, C; Gil-Montoya, JA	Oral lichen planus: controversies surrounding malignant transformation	219	235	Oral Dis.	2008	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Narrative review	Potentially malignant; potentially malignant condition; premalignant lesion

25	Mello, FW; Miguel, AFP; Dutra, KL; Porporatti, AL; Warnakulasuriya, S; Guerra, ENS; Rivero, ERC	Prevalence of oral potentially malignant disorders: A systematic review and meta-analysis	217	235	J. Oral Pathol. Med.	2018	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine; Pathology	Systematic review	Oral potentially malignant disorder
26	Fitzpatrick, SG; Hirsch, SA; Gordon, SC	The malignant transformation of oral lichen planus and oral lichenoid lesions A systematic review	200	229	J. Am. Dent. Assoc.	2014	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Systematic review	Potentially premalignant disorder; premalignant change; premalignant lesion
27	González-Moles, MA; Warnakulasuriya, S; González-Ruiz, I; González-Ruiz, L; Ayén, A; Lenouvel, D; Ruiz-Avila, I; Ramos-García, P	Worldwide prevalence of oral lichen planus: A systematic review and meta-analysis	199	210	Oral Dis.	2021	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Systematic review	Oral potentially malignant disorder
28	van der Meij, EH; Mast, H; van der Waal, I	The possible premalignant character of oral lichen planus and oral lichenoid lesions: A prospective five-year follow-up study of 192 patients	199	213	Oral Oncol.	2007	Oncology; Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Cohort study	Premalignant
29	Patton, LL; Epstein, JB; Kerr, AR	Adjunctive techniques for oral cancer examination and lesion diagnosis - A systematic review of the literature	194	221	J. Am. Dent. Assoc.	2008	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Systematic review	Oral premalignant lesion; premalignant disease; premalignant lesion; premalignant mucosal lesion; premalignancy
30	Farhi, D; Dupin, N	Pathophysiology, etiologic factors, and clinical management of	192	225	Clin. Dermatol.	2010	Dermatology	Narrative review	Premalignant

		oral lichen planus, part I: facts and controversies							
31	Wei, JE; Xie, GX; Zhou, ZT; Shi, P; Qiu, YP; Zheng, XJ; Chen, TL; Su, MM; Zhao, AH; Jia, W	Salivary metabolite signatures of oral cancer and leukoplakia	185	210	Int. J. Cancer	2011	Oncology	Case-control study	Oral precancerous lesion; precancerous lesion
32	Scully, C; Bagan, JV	Oral squamous cell carcinoma: overview of current understanding of aetiopathogenesis and clinical implications	185	212	Oral Dis.	2009	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Narrative review	Potentially malignant oral disorder; potentially malignant oral disorder; potentially malignant disorder; premalignant disease.
33	Hsue, SS; Wang, WC; Chen, CH; Lin, CC; Chen, YK; Lin, LM	Malignant transformation in 1458 patients with potentially malignant oral mucosal disorders: a follow-up study based in a Taiwanese hospital	183	194	J. Oral Pathol. Med.	2007	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine; Pathology	Cross-sectional study	Potentially malignant oral mucosal disorder; potentially malignant oral epithelial lesion; potentially pre-malignant oral lesion; oral precancerous lesion; premalignant oral lesion
34	Aghbari, SMH; Abushouk, AI; Attia, A; Elmaraezy, A; Menshawy, A; Ahmed, MS; Elsaadany, BA; Ahmed, EM	Malignant transformation of oral lichen planus and oral lichenoid lesions: A meta-analysis of 20095 patient data	176	198	Oral Oncol.	2017	Oncology; Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Systematic review	Premalignant
35	Carbone, M; Arduino, PG; Carrozzo, M; Gandolfo, S; Argiolas, MR; Bertolusso, G; Conrotto, D; Pentenero, M; Broccoletti, R	Course of oral lichen planus: a retrospective study of 808 northern Italian patients	176	188	Oral Dis.	2009	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Cross-sectional study	Potentially premalignant; potentially malignant
36	Gupta, S; Jawanda, MK	Oral Lichen Planus: An Update on Etiology, Pathogenesis, Clinical	173	192	Indian J. Dermatol.	2015	Dermatology	Narrative review	Oral cancer-correlated

		Presentation, Diagnosis and Management							
37	Tsao, AS; Liu, D; Martin, J; Tang, XM; Lee, JJ; El-Naggar, AK; Wistuba, I; Culotta, KS; Mao, L; Gillenwater, A; Sagesaka, YM; Hong, WK; Papadimitrakopoulou, V	Phase II Randomized, Placebo-Controlled Trial of Green Tea Extract in Patients with High-Risk Oral Premalignant Lesions	171	188	Cancer Prev. Res.	2009	Oncology	Clinical trial	Oral premalignant lesion; premalignant conditions; premalignancy
38	Warnakulasuriya, S; Kerr, AR	Oral Cancer Screening: Past, Present, and Future	163	171	J. Dent. Res.	2021	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Narrative review	Oral potentially malignant disorder; premalignant
39	González-Moles, MA; Ruiz-Avila, I; González-Ruiz, L; Ayén, A; Gil-Montoya, JA; Ramos-García, P	Malignant transformation risk of oral lichen planus: A systematic review and comprehensive meta-analysis	159	170	Oral Oncol.	2019	Oncology; Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Systematic review	Oral potentially malignant disorder; premalignant
40	Payeras, MR; Cherubini, K; Figueiredo, MA; Salum, FG	Oral lichen planus: Focus on etiopathogenesis	155	177	Arch. Oral Biol.	2013	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Narrative review	Potentially malignant oral disorder; potentially malignant disorder;
41	Abati, S; Bramati, C; Bondi, S; Lissoni, A; Trimarchi, M	Oral Cancer and Precancer: A Narrative Review on the Relevance of Early Diagnosis	153	170	Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health	2020	Environmental Sciences; Public, Environmental & Occupational Health	Narrative review	Oral precancer; precancerous lesion; potentially premalignant lesions; premalignant lesions of the oral mucosa; premalignancy; potentially malignant lesions; potentially malignant oral epithelial lesions
42	Warnakulasuriya, S	Clinical features and presentation of oral potentially malignant disorders	153	183	Oral Surg. Oral Med. Oral Pathol. Oral Radiol.	2018	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Narrative review	Oral potentially malignant disorder; potentially malignant disorder; potentially premalignant oral epithelial lesions; precancer; precancerous; premalignant lesions; intra-epithelial neoplasia

43	Giuliani, M; Troiano, G; Cordaro, M; Corsalini, M; Gioco, G; Lo Muzio, L; Pignatelli, P; Lajolo, C	Rate of malignant transformation of oral lichen planus: A systematic review	152	166	Oral Dis.	2019	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Systematic review	Potentially malignant disorders; oral precancerous lesions
44	Lodi, G; Franchini, R; Warnakulasuriya, S; Varoni, EM; Sardella, A; Kerr, AR; Carrassi, A; MacDonald, LCI; Worthington, HV	Interventions for treating oral leukoplakia to prevent oral cancer	147	158	Cochrane Database Syst Rev.	2016	Medicine, General & Internal	Systematic review	Potentially malignant disorder; oral precursor lesion; oral premalignant lesion
45	Warnakulasuriya, S; Kovacevic, T; Madden, P; Coupland, VH; Sperandio, M; Odell, E; Moller, H	Factors predicting malignant transformation in oral potentially malignant disorders among patients accrued over a 10-year period in South East England	143	153	J. Oral Pathol. Med.	2011	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine; Pathology	Cross-sectional study	Oral potentially malignant disorder; potentially malignant disorders of the oral cavity; precancer
46	Warnakulasuriya, S	Oral potentially malignant disorders: A comprehensive review on clinical aspects and management	142	155	Oral Oncol.	2020	Oncology; Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Narrative review	Oral potentially malignant disorder; potentially malignant; precancer; premalignancy
47	Zhang, LW; Poh, CF; Williams, M; Laronde, DM; Berean, K; Gardner, PJ; Jiang, HJ; Wu, L; Lee, JJ; Rosin, MP	Loss of Heterozygosity (LOH) Profiles-Validated Risk Predictors for Progression to Oral Cancer	142	150	Cancer Prev. Res.	2012	Oncology	Cohort study	Oral precancer; oral premalignant lesion; premalignant lesion
48	Awan, KH; Morgan, PR; Warnakulasuriya, S	Evaluation of an autofluorescence based imaging system (VELscope™) in the detection of oral potentially malignant	142	172	Oral Oncol.	2011	Oncology; Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Cross-sectional study	Oral potentially malignant disorder

		disorders and benign keratoses							
49	Dionne, KR; Warnakulasuriya, S; Zain, RB; Cheong, SC	Potentially malignant disorders of the oral cavity: Current practice and future directions in the clinic and laboratory	140	153	Int. J. Cancer	2015	Oncology	Narrative review	Potentially malignant disorder of the oral cavity; oral potentially malignant disorder; precancerous lesion; premalignant lesion
50	Lodi, G; Pellicano, R; Carrozzo, M	Hepatitis C virus infection and lichen planus: a systematic review with meta-analysis	140	151	Oral Dis.	2010	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Systematic review	Potentially malignant disorder
51	Kurago, ZB	Etiology and pathogenesis of oral lichen planus: an overview	139	157	Oral Surg. Oral Med. Oral Pathol. Oral Radiol.	2016	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Narrative review	Precursor to oral squamous cell carcinoma
52	Shih, YH; Wang, TH; Shieh, TM; Tseng, YH	Oral Submucous Fibrosis: A Review on Etiopathogenesis, Diagnosis, and Therapy	134	146	Int. J. Mol. Sci.	2019	Biochemistry & Molecular Biology; Chemistry, Multidisciplinary	Narrative review	Precancerous disorder; potentially malignant lesion; potentially malignant condition; potentially malignant oral disorder; oral precancer; precancerous lesion
53	Aguirre-Urizar, JM; de Mendoza, ILI; Warnakulasuriya, S	Malignant transformation of oral leukoplakia: Systematic review and meta-analysis of the last 5 years	132	140	Oral Dis.	2021	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Systematic review	Oral potentially malignant disorder
54	Dost, F; Le Cao, K; Ford, PJ; Ades, C; Farah, CS	Malignant transformation of oral epithelial dysplasia: a real-world evaluation of histopathologic grading	132	144	Oral Surg. Oral Med. Oral Pathol. Oral Radiol.	2014	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Cross-sectional study	Oral potentially malignant disorder; malignant disorders of the oral cavity; precursor lesion; precancerous;

55	van der Waal, I	Potentially malignant disorders of the oral and oropharyngeal mucosa; present concepts of management	131	149	Oral Oncol.	2010	Oncology; Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Narrative review	Potentially malignant disorders of the oral mucosa; potentially malignant disorder
56	Carrozzo, M; Porter, S; Mercadante, V; Fedele, S	Oral lichen planus: A disease or a spectrum of tissue reactions? Types, causes, diagnostic algorithms, prognosis, management strategies	130	151	Periodontol. 2000	2019	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Narrative review	Oral potentially malignant disorder
57	Wang, YY; Tail, YH; Wang, WC; Chen, CY; Kao, YH; Chen, YK; Chen, CH	Malignant transformation in 5071 southern Taiwanese patients with potentially malignant oral mucosal disorders	129	134	BMC Oral Health	2014	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Cross-sectional study	Potentially malignant oral mucosal disorder; oral potentially malignant disorder; precancerous lesion; precancerous oral lesion
58	van der Waal, I	Oral lichen planus and oral lichenoid lesions; a critical appraisal with emphasis on the diagnostic aspects	129	138	Med. Oral Patol. Oral Cir. Bucal	2009	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Narrative review	Potentially malignant disorder
59	Choudhari, SK; Chaudhary, M; Gadbail, AR; Sharma, A; Tekade, S	Oxidative and antioxidative mechanisms in oral cancer and precancer: A review	127	146	Oral Oncol.	2014	Oncology; Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Narrative review	Oral precancer; potentially malignant disorder; precancerous lesion; oral premalignant lesion
60	van der Waal, I	Oral potentially malignant disorders: Is malignant transformation predictable and preventable?	116	129	Med. Oral Patol. Oral Cir. Bucal	2014	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Narrative review	Oral potentially malignant disorder; potentially malignant disorder; oral potentially malignant lesion; premalignant; precancerous
61	Odell, E; Kujan, O; Warnakulasuriya, S; Sloan, P	Oral epithelial dysplasia: Recognition, grading and clinical significance	114	116	Oral Dis.	2021	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Narrative review	Oral potentially malignant disorder; precursor lesion; precancerous

62	Pitiyage, G; Tilakaratne, WM; Tavassoli, M; Warnakulasuriya, S	Molecular markers in oral epithelial dysplasia: review	114	126	J. Oral Pathol. Med.	2009	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine; Pathology	Narrative review	Potentially malignant disorder of the oral mucosa; precursor lesion; precancerous lesions or conditions
63	Vitale-Cross, L; Molinolo, AA; Martin, D; Younis, RH; Maruyama, T; Patel, V; Chen, WJ; Schneider, A; Gutkind, JS	Metformin Prevents the Development of Oral Squamous Cell Carcinomas from Carcinogen-Induced Premalignant Lesions	112	123	Cancer Prev. Res.	2012	Oncology	in vitro or ex vivo (laboratory) study	Preneoplastic precursor; premalignant lesion; oral premalignant lesion; premalignant oral lesion
64	Mehrotra, R; Gupta, DK	Exciting new advances in oral cancer diagnosis: avenues to early detection	112	131	Head Neck Oncol.	2011	Oncology	Narrative review	Potentially precancerous; oral precancerous lesion; precancerous lesions; premalignant lesion; premalignant oral diseases
65	Chiang, CP; Chang, JYF; Wang, YP; Wu, YH; Lu, SY; Sun, A	Oral lichen planus - Differential diagnoses, serum autoantibodies, hematinic deficiencies, and management	110	122	J. Formos. Med. Assoc.	2018	Medicine, General & Internal	Narrative review	Oral potentially malignant disorder; premalignant
66	Welikala, RA; Remagnino, P; Lim, JH; Chan, CS; Rajendran, S; Kallarakkal, TG; Zain, RB; Jayasinghe, RD; Rimal, J; Kerr, AR; Amtha, R; Patil, K; Tilakaratne, WM; Gibson, J; Cheong, SC; Barman, SA	Automated Detection and Classification of Oral Lesions Using Deep Learning for Early Detection of Oral Cancer	109	111	IEEE Access	2020	Computer Science, Information Systems; Engineering, Electrical & Electronic; Telecommunications	Cross-sectional study	Oral potentially malignant disorder
67	Yardimci, G; Kutlubay, Z; Engin, B; Tuzun, Y	Precancerous lesions of oral mucosa	108	128	World J. Clin. Cases	2014	Medicine, General & Internal	Narrative review	Potentially malignant disorder; precancerous lesions of oral mucosa; precancer; oral premalignant lesion; premalignant disorder

68	Tan, YH; Wang, ZH; Xu, MT; Li, BW; Huang, Z; Qin, SY; Nice, EC; Tang, J; Huang, CH	Oral squamous cell carcinomas: state of the field and emerging directions	107	117	Int. J. Oral Sci.	2023	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Narrative review	Oral potentially malignant disorder; potentially malignant lesion; precancerous squamous intraepithelial neoplasia; premalignant lesion
69	Saintigny, P; Zhang, L; Fan, YH; El-Naggar, AK; Papadimitrakopoulou, VA; Feng, L; Lee, JJ; Kim, ES; Hong, WK; Mao, L	Gene Expression Profiling Predicts the Development of Oral Cancer	107	113	Cancer Prev. Res.	2011	Oncology	Cohort study	Oral premalignant lesion
70	Tsai, MT; Lee, HC; Lee, CK; Yu, CH; Chen, HM; Chiang, CP; Chang, CC; Wang, YM; Yang, CC	Effective indicators for diagnosis of oral cancer using optical coherence tomography	107	114	Opt. Express	2008	Optics	Cross-sectional study	Oral precancer; precancer lesion; oral premalignant lesion
71	Brennan, M; Migliorati, CA; Lockhart, PB; Wray, D; Al-Hashimi, I; Axéll, T; Bruce, AJ; Carpenter, W; Eisenberg, E; Epstein, JB; Holmstrup, P; Jontell, M; Nair, R; Sasser, H; Schifter, M; Silverman, B; Thongprasom, K; Thornhill, M; Warnakulasuriya, S; van der Waal, I	Management of oral epithelial dysplasia:: a review	107	122	Oral Surg. Oral Med. Oral Pathol. Oral Radiol. Endod.	2007	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Narrative review	Potentially malignant lesion; precursor lesion; oral precancer; precancer; precancerous lesion; precancerous condition; oral precancerous lesion; premalignant lesion; premalignant oral lesion;
72	Brouns, EREA; Baart, JA; Karagozoglu, KH; Aartman, IHA;	Malignant transformation of oral leukoplakia in a well-defined cohort of 144 patients	106	113	Oral Dis.	2014	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Cohort study	Potentially malignant disorder of the oral mucosa; potentially malignant disorder;

	Bloemena, E; van der Waal, I								
73	Kerr, AR; Warnakulasuriya, S; Mighell, AJ; Dietrich, T; Nasser, M; Rimal, J; Jalil, A; Bornstein, MM; Nagao, T; Fortune, F; Hazarey, VH; Reichart, PA; Silverman, S; Johnson, NW	A systematic review of medical interventions for oral submucous fibrosis and future research opportunities	106	112	Oral Dis.	2011	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Systematic review	Potentially malignant oral disorder; potentially malignant disorder of the oral cavity; malignant oral mucosal lesion; potentially malignant oral disease; potentially malignant oral lesion; oral precancer
74	Ganly, I; Yang, LY; Giese, RA; Hao, YH; Nossa, CW; Morris, LGT; Rosenthal, M; Migliacci, J; Kelly, D; Tseng, WZ; Hu, JY; Li, HL; Brown, S; Pei, ZH	Periodontal pathogens are a risk factor of oral cavity squamous cell carcinoma, independent of tobacco and alcohol and human papillomavirus	105	114	Int. J. Cancer	2019	Oncology	Case-control study	Premalignant lesion; oral premalignant lesion
75	McCullough, MJ; Prasad, G; Farah, CS	Oral mucosal malignancy and potentially malignant lesions: an update on the epidemiology, risk factors, diagnosis and management	105	115	Aust. Dent. J.	2010	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Narrative review	Potentially malignant lesion; potentially malignant oral mucosal lesion; potentially malignant mucosal lesion; precursor lesion; precancerous oral lesion
76	Bombeccari, GP; Guzzi, G; Tettamanti, M; Gianni, AB; Baj, A; Pallotti, F; Spadari, F	Oral lichen planus and malignant transformation: a longitudinal cohort study	104	121	Oral Surg. Oral Med. Oral Pathol. Oral Radiol. Endod.	2011	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Cohort study	Potentially malignant disorder; precancerous condition; premalignant condition
77	Song, XW; Yang, XH; Narayanan, R; Shankar, V; Ethiraj, S; Wang, X; Duan, N; Ni, YH; Hu, QG; Zare, RN	Oral squamous cell carcinoma diagnosed from saliva metabolic profiling	102	109	Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.	2020	Multidisciplinary Sciences	Cross-sectional study	Precancerous; premalignant lesion; premalignancy

78	Sawhney, M; Rohatgi, N; Kaur, J; Shishodia, S; Sethi, G; Gupta, SD; Deo, SVS; Shukla, NK; Aggarwal, BB; Ralhan, R	Expression of NF-κB parallels COX-2 expression in oral precancer and cancer:: Association with smokeless tobacco	102	113	Int. J. Cancer	2007	Oncology	Cross-sectional study	Oral precancerous lesion; precancerous lesion; premalignant lesion
79	Singh, SP; Deshmukh, A; Chaturvedi, P; Krishna, CM	<i>In vivo</i> Raman spectroscopic identification of premalignant lesions in oral buccal mucosa	101	103	J. Biomed. Opt.	2012	Biochemical Research Methods; Optics; Radiology, Nuclear Medicine & Medical Imaging	Case-control study	Precancer; precancerous condition; premalignant lesion in oral buccal mucosa; premalignant lesion; premalignant condition; premalignant patch; premalignant pathology; premalignant pathosis;
80	Amer, A; Galvin, S; Healy, CM; Moran, GP	The Microbiome of Potentially Malignant Oral Leukoplakia Exhibits Enrichment for <i>Fusobacterium</i>, <i>Leptotrichia</i>, <i>Campylobacter</i>, and <i>Rothia</i> Species	100	104	Front. Microbiol.	2017	Microbiology	Cross-sectional study	Potentially malignant oral leukoplakia; potentially malignant precursor
81	Brocklehurst, P; Kujan, O; O'Malley, LA; Ogden, G; Shepherd, S; Glenny, AM	Screening programmes for the early detection and prevention of oral cancer	100	113	Cochrane Database Syst Rev.	2013	Medicine, General & Internal	Systematic review	Potentially malignant disorder; precancer
82	Zahran, F; Ghalwash, D; Shaker, O; Al-Johani, K; Scully, C	Salivary microRNAs in oral cancer	99	104	Oral Dis.	2015	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Case-control study	Potentially malignant disorder; oral potentially malignant disorder; precursor lesion
83	Wilder-Smith, P; Lee, K; Guo, SG; Zhang, J; Osann, K; Chen, ZP; Messadi, D	In Vivo Diagnosis of Oral Dysplasia and Malignancy Using Optical Coherence Tomography: Preliminary Studies in 50 Patients	99	112	Lasers Surg. Med.	2009	Dermatology; Surgery	Case-control study	Oral premalignancy

84	Hernandez, BY; Zhu, XM; Goodman, MT; Gatewood, R; Mendiola, P; Quinata, K; Paulino, YC	Betel nut chewing, oral premalignant lesions, and the oral microbiome	98	108	PLoS One	2017	Multidisciplinary Sciences	Cross-sectional study	Precursor lesion; precancerous; oral premalignant lesion; premalignant oral lesion
85	Amagasa, T; Yamashiro, M; Uzawa, N	Oral premalignant lesions: from a clinical perspective	98	117	Int. J. Clin. Oncol.	2011	Oncology	Narrative review	Oral precancerous lesion; precancerous lesion; oral premalignant lesion; premalignant lesion
86	Smith, J; Rattay, T; McConkey, C; Helliwell, T; Mehanna, H	Biomarkers in dysplasia of the oral cavity: A systematic review	98	109	Oral Oncol.	2009	Oncology; Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Systematic review	Potentially precancerous lesion; precancerous lesion; precursor of oral cancer
87	Ho, MW; Risk, JM; Woolgar, JA; Field, EA; Field, JK; Steele, JC; Rajlawat, BP; Triantafyllou, A; Rogers, SN; Lowe, D; Shaw, RJ	The clinical determinants of malignant transformation in oral epithelial dysplasia	97	112	Oral Oncol.	2012	Oncology; Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Cohort study	Potentially malignant oral; premalignant lesion
88	Rad, M; Hashemipoor, MA; Mojtahedi, A; Zarei, MR; Chamani, G; Kakoei, S; Izadi, N	Correlation between clinical and histopathologic diagnoses of oral lichen planus based on modified WHO diagnostic criteria	97	105	Oral Surg. Oral Med. Oral Pathol. Oral Radiol. Endod.	2009	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Cross-sectional study	Premalignant changes
89	Mallery, SR; Zwick, JC; Pei, P; Tong, M; Larsen, PE; Shumway, BS; Lu, B; Fields, HW; Mumper, RJ; Stoner, GD	Topical application of a bioadhesive black raspberry gel modulates gene expression and reduces cyclooxygenase 2 protein in human premalignant oral lesions	96	111	Cancer Res.	2008	Oncology	Clinical trial	Premalignant oral lesion; premalignant lesion; precursor to oral SCC; precancerous oral lesion

90	Brailo, V; Vucicevic-Boras, V; Lukac, J; Biocina-Lukenda, D; Alajbeg, IZ; Milenovic, A; Balija, M	Salivary and serum interleukin 1 beta, interleukin 6 and tumor necrosis factor alpha in patients with leukoplakia and oral cancer	95	110	Med. Oral Patol. Oral Cir. Bucal	2012	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Case-control study	Oral precancerous lesion
91	Maheswari, TNU; Nivedhitha, MS; Ramani, P	Expression profile of salivary micro RNA-21 and 31 in oral potentially malignant disorders	94	94	Braz. Oral Res.	2020	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Case-control study	Oral potentially malignant disorder; oral premalignant lesion; precancer lesion; precancer condition
92	Yu, JS; Chen, YT; Chiang, WF; Hsiao, YC; Chu, LJ; See, LC; Wu, CS; Tu, HT; Chen, HW; Chen, CC; Liao, WC; Chang, YT; Wu, CC; Lin, CY; Liu, SY; Chiou, ST; Chia, SL; Chang, KP; Chien, CY; Chang, SW; Chang, CJ; Young, JD; Pao, CC; Chang, YS; Hartwell, LH	Saliva protein biomarkers to detect oral squamous cell carcinoma in a high-risk population in Taiwan	94	100	Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci. U. S. A.	2016	Multidisciplinary Sciences	Cohort study	Oral potentially malignant disorder; potential malignant disorder
93	Saini, R; Lee, NV; Liu, KYP; Poh, CF	Prospects in the Application of Photodynamic Therapy in Oral Cancer and Premalignant Lesions	93	103	Cancers	2016	Oncology	Narrative review	Oral precancer; precancer of the head and neck; premalignant lesion; oral premalignant lesion; precancerous lesion
94	Benckekroun, MT; Saintigny, P; Thomas, SM; El-Naggar, AK; Papadimitrakopoulou, V; Ren, HN; Lang, WH; Fan, YH; Huang, JH; Feng, L; Lee, JJ; Kim, ES; Hong, WK;	Epidermal Growth Factor Receptor Expression and Gene Copy Number in the Risk of Oral Cancer	93	102	Cancer Prev. Res.	2010	Oncology	Cross-sectional study	Premalignant lesion of the oral cavity; oral premalignant lesion

	Johnson, FM; Grandis, JR; Mao, L								
95	Torres-Rendon, A; Roy, S; Craig, GT; Speight, PM	Expression of Mcm2, geminin and Ki67 in normal oral mucosa, oral epithelial dysplasias and their corresponding squamous-cell carcinomas	93	106	Br. J. Cancer	2009	Oncology	Case-control study	Premalignant
96	Awadallah, M; Idle, M; Patel, K; Kademani, D	Management update of potentially premalignant oral epithelial lesions	92	105	Oral Surg. Oral Med. Oral Pathol. Oral Radiol.	2018	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Narrative review	Oral potentially malignant disorder; premalignant disorder; potentially premalignant oral epithelial lesion; oral premalignant lesion; premalignant disorder; premalignant lesion; premalignant disease; precursor to OSCC; precancerous lesion
97	Olson, MA; Rogers, RS; Bruce, AJ	Oral lichen planus	92	108	Clin. Dermatol.	2016	Dermatology	Narrative review	Precancerous
98	Walvekar, RR; Chaukar, DA; Deshpande, MS; Pai, PS; Chaturvedi, P; Kakade, A; Kane, SV; D'Cruz, AK	Verrucous carcinoma of the oral cavity: A clinical and pathological study of 101 cases	91	99	Oral Oncol.	2009	Oncology; Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine	Cross-sectional study	Premalignant lesion; premalignant changes
99	Lodi, G; Porter, S	Management of potentially malignant disorders: evidence and critique	91	104	J. Oral Pathol. Med.	2008	Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine; Pathology	Narrative review	Potentially malignant disorder; potentially malignant disorder of the oral mucosa; potentially malignant disease; potentially malignant oral lesion; potentially malignant disease of the oral mucosa; potentially malignant oral mucosal disease; oral precancer
100	Morse, DE; Psoter, WJ; Cleveland, D; Cohen,	Smoking and drinking in relation to oral cancer and oral epithelial dysplasia	91	107	Cancer Causes Control	2007	Oncology; Public, Environmental & Occupational Health	Cross-sectional study	Potentially premalignant oral lesion; oral precancer; precancerous condition; precancerous lesion; premalignant lesion

D; Mohit-Tabatabai, M;
Kosis, DL; Eisenberg, E

*WoS Core Collection, BIOSIS Citation Index, Chinese Science Citation Database, Data Citation Index, Russian Citation Index, and SciELO Citation. Index

Table 3. Top contributing journals based on bibliometric analysis.

Journal	Total
Oral Diseases	13
Oral Oncology	12
Journal of Oral Pathology & Medicine	12
Oral Surgery, Oral Medicine, Oral Pathology, and Oral Radiology	10
Cancer Prevention Research	5
International Journal of Cancer	4
Medicina Oral, Patologia Oral, Cirugia Bucal	3
The Journal of the American Dental Association	2
Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences	2
Journal of Dental Research	2
Head & Neck	2
Cochrane Database of Systematic Reviews	2
Clinics in Dermatology	2
Archives of Dermatological Research	1
Archives of Oral Biology	1
Australian Dental Journal	1
BMC Oral Health	1
Brazilian Oral Research	1
British Journal of Cancer	1
CA: A Cancer Journal for Clinicians	1
Cancer Causes Control	1
Cancer Research	1
Cancers	1
Frontiers in Microbiology	1
Head Neck Oncology	1
IEEE Access	1
Indian Journal of Dermatology	1
International Journal of Clinical and Experimental Pathology	1

International Journal of Clinical Oncology	1
International Journal of Environmental Research and Public Health	1
International Journal of Molecular Sciences	1
International Journal of Oral Science	1
Journal of Biomedical Optics	1
Journal of Cancer Research and Therapeutics	1
Journal of the Formosan Medical Association	1
Lasers in Surgery and Medicine	1
Mayo Clinic Proceedings	1
Optics Express	1
Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery Clinics of North America	1
Periodontology 2000	1
PLoS One	1
World Journal of Clinical Cases	1

Table 4. Characteristics of the 100 most cited articles by Authors' country, first author's specialty, and institutional affiliation.

Article Number*	First Author's Country	First Author's Specialty	Institutional affiliation of correspondent author
1	UK	Oral medicine	King's College London, London, UK
2	USA	Oral pathology	MUSC College of Dental Medicine, Charleston, USA
3	USA	Oral pathology	The University of Texas School of Dentistry at Houston, Houston, USA
4	Chile	Oral medicine/Oral pathology	University of Talca (UTALCA), Maule Region, Chile
5	USA	Biochemistry	University of the Pacific, Arthur A. Dugoni School of Dentistry, San Francisco, USA
6	Netherlands	Oral pathology	VU University Medical Center (VUmc), Academic Centre for Dentistry Amsterdam (ACTA), Amsterdam, The Netherlands
7	UK	Oral medicine	King's College London, London, UK
8	UK	Oral medicine	King's College London, London, UK
9	India	Oral pathology	YMT Dental College and Hospital, Navi Mumbai, India
10	UK	Oral pathology	University of Sheffield, Sheffield, UK
11	India	Oral pathology	Uttar Pradesh Dental College and Research Centre, Lucknow, India
12	USA	Periodontology	VU University Medical Center (VUmc), Academic Centre for Dentistry Amsterdam (ACTA), Amsterdam, The Netherlands
13	India	Oral pathology	Post Graduate Institute of Dental Sciences, Uttar Pradesh, India
14	UK	Oral pathology	University of Sheffield, Sheffield, UK
15	USA	Oral pathology	Texas A&M University, College of Dentistry, Dallas, USA
16	UK	Oral medicine	King's College London, London, UK
17	UK	Oral medicine	King's College London, London, UK
18	Jordan	Oral medicine	Jordan University of Science and Technology, Irbid, Jordan

19	UK	Head and Neck Surgery	University Hospitals Coventry and Warwickshire, Coventry, UK
20	USA	Head and Neck Surgery	Division of Oral Diagnosis and Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery, Mayo Clinic, Rochester, USA
21	Italy	Head and Neck Surgery	Humanitas Clinical and Research Center, Milano, Italy
22	Australia	Oral and maxillofacial surgery	The University of Queensland, Queensland, Australia
23	Finland	Oral pathology	University of Turku, Lemminka Isenkatu, Finland
24	Spain	Oral medicine	University of Granada, Granada, Spain
25	Brazil	Oral pathology	Federal University of Santa Catarina, Florian opolis, Brazil
26	USA	Oral pathology	Case Western Reserve University, Cleveland, USA
27	Spain	Oral medicine	University of Granada, Granada, Spain
28	Netherlands	Oral and maxillofacial surgery	Erasmus Medical Centre, Rotterdam, Netherlands
29	USA	Oral medicine	University of North Carolina Chapel Hill, USA
30	France	Dermatology	Hôpital Cochin, Université Descartes, Paris, France
31	China	Medicine	University of North Carolina at Greensboro, North Carolina Research Campus, Kannapolis, USA
32	UK	Oral medicine	University College London, London, UK
33	Taiwan	Oral pathology	Kaohsiung Medical University Hospital, Kaohsiung, Taiwan
34	Yemen	Public health	Beni Suef University, Beni Suef, Egypt
35	Italy	Oral medicine/Oral pathology	University of Turin, Turin, Italy
36	India	Oral pathology	Swami Devi Dyal Hospital and Dental College, Golpura, Barwala, India.
37	USA	Head and Neck Oncology	Univ Texas MD Anderson Cancer Centre, Houston, USA
38	UK	Oral medicine	King's College London, London, UK

39	Spain	Oral medicine	University of Granada, Granada, Spain
40	Brazil	Oral medicine	Pontificia Universidade Catolica Rio Grande do Sul PUCRS, Porto Alegre, Brazil.
41	Italy	Oral medicine	University Vita-Salute, Milano, Italy
42	UK	Oral medicine	King's College London, London, UK
43	Italy	Oral medicine/Oral pathology	University of Foggia, Foggia, Italy
44	Italy	Oral medicine	Università degli Studi di Milano, Milan, Italy
45	UK	Oral medicine	King's College London, London, UK
46	UK	Oral medicine	King's College London, London, UK
47	Canada	Oral pathology	Cancer Agency, Department of Cancer Control Research, British Columbia, Canada
48	UK	Oral medicine	King's College London, London, UK
49	Malaysia	Neurology	Taman Perindustrian UEP, Selangor Darul, Malaysia
50	Italy	Oral medicine	University of Newcastle upon Tyne, Newcastle upon Tyne, UK
51	USA	Oral pathology	Augusta University, Augusta, USA
52	Taiwan	Public health	Kaohsiung Medical University, Kaohsiung, Taiwan
53	Spain	Oral medicine	University of the Basque Country/EHU, Lejona, Spain
54	Australia	Oral medicine/Oral pathology	University of Queensland, UQ Centre for Clinical Research, Herston, Australia
55	Netherlands	Oral pathology	VU University Medical Center (VUmc), Academic Centre for Dentistry Amsterdam (ACTA), Amsterdam, The Netherlands
56	UK	Oral medicine	UCL Eastman Dental Institute, University College London, London, UK
57	Taiwan	N/I	Kaohsiung Med University of Hospital, Kaohsiung, Taiwan
58	Netherlands	Oral pathology	VU University Medical Center (VUmc), Academic Centre for Dentistry Amsterdam (ACTA), Amsterdam, The Netherlands
59	India	Oral pathology	Yerala Dental College and Hospital, Kharghar, Mumbai, India

60	Netherlands	Oral pathology	VU University Medical Center (VUmc), Academic Centre for Dentistry Amsterdam (ACTA), Amsterdam, The Netherlands
61	UK	Oral medicine/Oral pathology	The University of Western Australia, Perth, Australia.
62	Sri Lanka	Oral pathology	King's College London, London, UK
63	USA	Biology	Tohoku University, Sendai, Japan
64	India	General pathology	Moti Lal Nehru Medical College, Allahabad, India
65	Taiwan	Oral pathology	National Taiwan University Hospital, Taipei, Taiwan
66	UK	Imaging science	Kingston University, Kingston upon Thames, UK
67	Turkey	Dermatology	Istanbul University, Cerrah Paşa Mh, Istanbul
68	China	N/I	West China Hospital, Sichuan University, Chengdu, China
69	USA	Oncology	University of Maryland Dental School, Baltimore, USA
70	Taiwan	Electronic Engineering	National Taiwan University, Taipei, Taiwan
71	USA	Oral medicine	VU University Medical Center (VUmc), Academic Centre for Dentistry Amsterdam (ACTA), Amsterdam, The Netherlands
72	Netherlands	Oral pathology	VU University Medical Center (VUmc), Academic Centre for Dentistry Amsterdam (ACTA), Amsterdam, The Netherlands
73	USA	Oral medicine	King's College London, London, UK
74	USA	Head and Neck Surgery	Department of Pathology and Laboratory Service, Veterans Affairs New York Harbor Health System, New York, USA
75	Australia	Oral medicine/Oral and maxillofacial surgery	The University of Melbourne, Carlton, Australia
76	Italy	Oral medicine/Oral and maxillofacial surgery	University of Milan, Milan, Italy
77	China	Chemistry	Medical School of Nanjing University, Nanjing, Jiangsu, China

78	India	Biochemistry	India Institute of Medical Sciences, New Delhi, India
79	India	Optics Engineering	Advanced Center for Treatment Research and Education in Cancer (ACTREC), Tata Memorial Center, Navi Mumbai, India
80	Ireland	Microbiology	Trinity College Dublin, Dublin Dental University Hospital, Dublin, Ireland
81	UK	Public health	The University of Manchester, Manchester, UK
82	Saudi Arabia	Oral medicine	Faculty of Dentistry, King Abdulaziz University, Jeddah, Saudi Arabia
83	USA	Oral medicine	University of California, Irvine, USA
84	USA	Epidemiology	University of Hawaii Cancer Center, Honolulu, USA
85	Japan	Oral and maxillofacial surgery	Tokyo Medical and Dental University, Tokyo, Japan
86	UK	Head and Neck Surgery	University Hospitals Coventry and Warwickshire, Coventry, UK
87	UK	Head and Neck Surgery	The University of Liverpool Cancer Research Centre, University of Liverpool, Liverpool, UK
88	Iran	Oral medicine	Kerman Medical University, Kerman, Iran
89	USA	Oral pathology	The Ohio State University, Columbus, USA
90	Croatia	Oral medicine	University of Zagreb, Zagreb, Croatia
91	India	Oral medicine	Saveetha University, Tamil Nadu, India
92	Taiwan	Molecular biology	Chang Gung University, Taoyuan, Taiwan
93	Canada	Oral medicine	University of British Columbia, Vancouver, Canada
94	USA	Oncology	University of Maryland Dental School, Baltimore, USA
95	UK	Oral pathology	University of Sheffield, Sheffield, UK
96	USA	Oral and maxillofacial surgery	North Memorial Medical Center, Department of Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery, Minneapolis, USA
97	USA	Dermatology	Mayo Clin, Department of Dermatology, Jacksonville, USA
98	India	Head and Neck Surgery	Tata Memorial Hospital, Mumbai, India

99	Italy	Oral medicine	Universita degli Studi di Milano, Milano, Italy
100	USA	Epidemiology	New York University College of Dentistry, New York, USA

*based on the citation rankings shown in Table 2.

The most frequently used keywords related to OPMD were “Oral Potentially Malignant Disorder” (n=28), “Potentially Malignant Disorder” (n=25), and “Premalignant Lesion” (n=25) (**Figure 4**). These terms reflect a trend towards increasingly adopting “OPMD” over time, particularly after 2017, while also emphasizing the continuing use of terms associated with "pre-malignant" (**Figures 5 and 6**).

Figure 4. Overall frequency of terms related to OPMD in the 100 most-cited articles.

Words' Frequency over Time

Figure 5. Frequency of terms related to OPMD in the 100 most-cited articles published between 2007 and 2024.

Trend Topics

Figure 6. Trends of terms related to OPMD over time.

A variety of non-standardized, former, or hybrid terms were identified in 60 articles and classified under the category "Other context". Additionally, in 15 publications, the use of such OPMD terminology was categorized as "Reflecting the terminology used in referenced studies", while 9 publications were classified under "Discussing the transition to OPMD terminology" (**Supplementary Appendix 2**). The terms include: "pre-malignant lesion", "pre-malignant condition", "oral pre-malignant lesion", "oral pre-malignant condition", "oral pre-malignant disorder", "pre-malignant oral lesion", "pre-malignant change", "pre-malignant lesion of the oral mucosa", "mucosal pre-malignant lesion", "potentially pre-malignant oral epithelial lesion", "pre-malignancy", "pre-cancerous condition", "pre-cancerous lesion", "oral pre-cancerous lesion", "oral pre-cancerous alteration", "pre-cancerous oral lesion", "pre-cancer", "oral pre-cancer", "precursor to oral SCC", "oral cancer-correlated", "intra-epithelial neoplasia", and others (**Table 2**). These terms were most found in articles published in 2007 (n=8), 2009 (n=8), and 2011 (n=7), with additional occurrences in 2008 (n=3), 2010 (n=5), 2012 (n=5), 2014 (n=5), 2015 (n=3), 2016 (n=5), 2017 (n=3), 2018 (n=2), 2019 (n=2), 2020 (n=2), 2021 (n=1), and 2023 (n=1).

The use of non-standardized or former terminology classified as "Other context" was observed in articles authored by researchers from various fields, including Oral Pathology (n=15), Oral Medicine (n=11), Head and Neck Surgery (n=6), Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery (n=3), Oral Medicine/Oral Pathology (n=2), Oral Medicine/Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery (n=2), Public Health (n=2), Epidemiology (n=2), Microbiology (n=1), Dermatology (n=2), Biochemistry (n=2), Chemistry (n=1), General Pathology (n=1), Periodontology (n=1), General Medicine (n=1), Head and Neck Oncology (n=1), Biology (n=1), Oncology (n=1), Electronic Engineering (n=1), Optical Engineering (n=1), and unspecified fields (n=2). Regarding journal specialties, the following fields were associated with the use of non-standardized terminology for OPMD in "Other context": Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine (n=19), Oncology (n=14), Oncology/ Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine (n=7), Dentistry, Oral Surgery & Medicine/ Pathology (n=3), Dermatology (n=3), Medicine, General & Internal (n=3), Multidisciplinary Sciences (n=2), Microbiology (n=1), Biochemical Research Methods/ Optics/ Radiology, Nuclear Medicine & Medical Imaging (n=1), Biochemistry & Molecular Biology/Chemistry, Multidisciplinary (n=1), Dermatology/ Surgery (n=1), Environmental Sciences/ Public, Environmental & Occupational Health (n=1), Oncology/ Pathology (n=1), Oncology/ Public, Environmental & Occupational Health (n=1), Optics (n=1), and Otorhinolaryngology/ Surgery (n=1).

A total of 545 authors were identified across the 100 selected articles, with collaboration networks among the authors of the most cited articles illustrated in **Figure 7**. The network clustering by coupling graph from Biblioshiny reveals three distinct clusters, each represented by a unique color and associated with specific terms related to oral potentially malignant disorders (OPMD). The red cluster exhibits the strongest association with the terms "oral potentially malignant disorder" (87.5% confidence) and "potentially malignant disorder" (81.2% confidence), alongside a moderate association with "pre-malignant" (55.9% confidence). In contrast, the blue cluster demonstrates a weaker but noticeable association with the same terms, with lower confidence levels: 18.8% for "potentially malignant disorder," 14.7% for "pre-malignant," and 10% for "oral potentially malignant disorder." The green cluster introduces related but distinct terms, such as "pre-malignant lesion" (52% confidence), "oral precancer" (60% confidence), and "oral precancerous lesion" (68.8% confidence). These findings highlight the complex interrelationship between terms associated with OPMD. The red cluster stands out with its strong focus on "oral potentially malignant disorder," suggesting it represents a central theme in the literature. The blue cluster, although sharing some overlapping terms, represents a lower confidence level, suggesting a secondary theme of research. In contrast, the green cluster focuses on terminology related to precancerous lesions and oral precancer, reflecting a less prominent but still significant theme within OPMD publications. Overall, this clustering pattern highlights the multifaceted nature of OPMD research, showcasing diverse conceptual frameworks and the integration of ideas across clusters.

Figure 7. Author collaboration networks in the most cited articles. Three clusters are shown (red, blue, and green), with one (red) indicating a strong association with the terms "oral potentially malignant disorder" and "potentially malignant disorder". Prominent authors often serve as central connectors in the network.

Geographically, articles using non-standardized keywords were predominantly authored by corresponding authors from Asia and the middle east (India, Taiwan, China, Japan, Iran, Jordan, Saudi Arabia; n=20), North America (USA, Canada; n=19), and Europe (UK, Netherlands, Italy, Croatia, Finland, France, Ireland, and Turkey; n=18). Few articles also originated from Oceania (Australia; n=1), South America (Chile; n=1), and Africa (Egypt; n=1) (**Table 2**). There was a notable tendency for institutions in the UK to adopt the term OPMD (**Figure 8**).

Figure 8. Use of OMPD terminology by leading authors and their institution.

4. DISCUSSION

This bibliometric analysis produced important findings regarding the use of various terminologies for OPMD in the 100 most-cited articles on this topic. It was observed that the term "OPMD," introduced by the expert working group coordinated by the WHO Collaborating Centre for Oral Cancer (Warnakulasuriya, Johnson & van der Waal, 2007) and enacted in the 4th edition of the WHO Classification of Head and Neck Tumours in 2017 (Reibel et al., 2017), was adopted by most of the highly cited publications after the release of their consensus paper in 2007. This adoption showed an increasing trend over time, accompanied by a shift away from the use of previous terminology, particularly among the most prolific authors and after its inclusion in the WHO's 2017 Classification of Head and Neck Tumors (Reibel et al., 2017). However, a significant proportion of these selected high-impact articles continued to use a range of non-standardized, former, or hybrid terms. It is noteworthy that, in some of the articles analyzed, these non-standardized terms were often employed within the context of discussing the transition to OPMD terminology or out of respect for the terminology used in the referenced studies.

Nonetheless, certain articles still used hybrid or outdated terms, such as “pre-malignant lesions”, “pre-malignant conditions”, or “oral pre-malignant lesions”, leading to inconsistency and some confusion (Warnakulasuriya et al., 2021). This diversity in language appears primarily in articles by researchers from fields such as Oral Medicine and Oral Pathology, potentially reflecting either individual preferences or a delay in adopting the term. This delay could result from the time gap between the WHO’s Collaborating Centre for Oral Cancer recommendation of OPMD and its integration into academic discourse. Additionally, a substantial number of studies were authored by specialists from diverse fields, including Head and Neck Surgery, Oral and Maxillofacial Surgery, General Pathology, Public Health, Chemistry, Epidemiology, Microbiology, Dermatology, Biochemistry, Periodontology, General Medicine, Head and Neck Oncology, Biology, Oncology, Electronic Engineering, and Optical Engineering. This variety of specialties may influence preferences in adopting terminology, especially in areas where terms like “precancer” or “pre-malignancy” are commonly used for other organs and tissues (WHO, 2021; Falcone et al., 2024; van de Nieuwenhof, van der Avoort & de Hullu, 2008).

Two cases from the current analysis illustrate this issue. The first involves an article by oncology specialists published in a journal in their field (Taoudi-Benchekroun et al., 2010). Although the article cites the publication that introduced the term OPMD, proposed by the WHO Collaborating Centre for Oral Cancer, it uses the terms “pre-malignant lesion of the oral cavity” and “oral pre-malignant lesion” without referring to OPMD. The second example is an article authored by a researcher in Optical Engineering, published in 2012 (Singh et al., 2012), five years after the OPMD term was proposed. This article does not cite any key references related to OPMD’s concept, epidemiology, or classification, instead using the term “pre-malignant” 68 times throughout the text.

In terms of journal specialties, the fields of Dentistry, Oral Surgery, Oral Medicine, and Oral Pathology were significantly associated with the use of non-standardized terminology for OPMD. This highlights the need for editorial-level discussions on the adoption of the OPMD concept. Additionally, a notable number of articles were published in other specialty fields, particularly in Oncology, supporting the idea that a journal’s area of specialty may influence terminology preferences.

When examining geographical distribution, articles using non-standardized keywords were primarily authored by researchers from Asia, North America, and Europe.

Given the variety of institutions across countries and languages, terminology differences may arise from regional language influences and the specific terms used in medical or dental fields. Institutions in non-English-speaking countries may contribute to non-standard terminology by translating or adapting terms into English (Monteiro et al., 2023). According to Monteiro et al. (2023), there is significant variation in the translation of terms related to OPMD across different native languages in European countries. Their editorial attributes this variation to translation challenges, particularly in Portuguese, Spanish, French, Italian, and Croatian. A tendency to adopt OMPD terminology was observed in articles from UK-based institutions, possibly reflecting the continuing education adopted in the country. Additionally, a workshop held by the WHO Collaborating Centre for Oral Cancer in the UK in 2005 discussed this terminology and related concepts (Warnakulasuriya, Johnson & van der Waal, 2007), bringing together key UK opinion leaders who trained many professionals across the country. This likely contributed to the widespread adoption of the term OPMD in UK publications.

Most of the selected articles focused on topics related to OPMD, including Malignant transformation, Miscellaneous, Management, Diagnosis, and Prognostic Biomarkers. Among OPMD, Oral Lichen Planus was the most frequently studied, likely due to its high prevalence (González-Moles et al., 2021). Most of these publications were narrative reviews, systematic reviews, or cross-sectional studies. Systematic and narrative reviews on OPMD were included as they are valuable information sources for clinicians and researchers. This underscores the importance of using standardized terminology (e.g. OPMD) in these manuscripts, as they often establish concepts for clinical practice and serve as a foundation for new scientific research. Despite their importance to clinical practice in OPMD management, we found a lack of clinical trials among the top 100 most cited articles. This may reflect the overall scarcity of such studies in the literature, as noted by Lodi et al. (2016) in their systematic review.

The United Kingdom produced the highest number of top 100 articles on OPMD, followed closely by the United States. Despite the significant contribution of the USA to the OPMD literature, it was also one of the main sources of articles that used non-standardized keywords. Despite the high prevalence of OPMDs in Asia (Mello et al., 2018) many Indian authors still tend to use the terms “precancer” or “pre-malignancy” due to unfamiliarity with the literature. The most cited article on OPMD was published by the WHO Collaborating Centre for Oral Cancer, addressing the nomenclature and

classification of OPMD, underscoring the concept's broad adoption and acceptance within the research community (Warnakulasuriya, Johnson & van der Waal, 2007).

As expected, a significant proportion of the most-cited OPMD articles published between 2007 and 2024 were concentrated in 2007 and 2016. This reflects the influence of publication age on citation volume; according to Brizan et al. (2016), articles often receive most of their citations within the first few years, with citation rates declining exponentially after reaching a peak.

The bibliometric network analysis reveals significant interconnections and influence among key researchers publishing on OPMDs between 2007 and 2024. The visualization highlights prominent authors such as Professors Saman Warnakulasuriya, van der Wall, Omar Kujan, Miguel Ángel González Moles, Ross Kerr, Paul Speight, Giovanni Lodi, Aguirre-Urizar, and others, who appear as central nodes due to their extensive contributions and frequent citations within the field. The strong connections among these authors suggest collaborative or referential relationships, underscoring their leading roles in shaping current understanding and terminology surrounding OPMDs. This interconnected network of authors also reflects an evolving approach to OPMD research, fostering the development of a unified terminology and understanding of malignancy risks in oral health. This bibliometric analysis highlights the importance of consistent terminology in the study of OPMD. Following the adoption of OPMD by the WHO Collaborating Centre for Oral Cancer in 2007 (Warnakulasuriya, Johnson & van der Waal, 2007), meaningful high-impact articles embraced this standardized term, marking a significant shift in the literature. However, a notable subset of these studies still uses non-standardized or hybrid terms like "pre-malignant lesions" and "oral precancerous conditions," leading to inconsistencies in terminology across the field. This variation in the terminology may stem from authors' disciplines, regional preferences, or a delay in adopting the WHO terminology.

5. CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, this analysis underscores the need for a unified approach to terminology, advocating for the global adoption of OPMD to enhance clarity and cohesion across studies. Encouraging the consistent use of OPMD terminology across different specialties and regions can strengthen professional understanding and support more informed treatment decisions for OPMD.

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APPENDIX 1

Table 1
The proposed items in the PRIBA to be used for reporting bibliometric studies, adapted from the PRISMA Checklist (<http://prismastatement.org/PRISMAStatement/Checklist.aspx>).

Section and topic	Item #	Proposed item to be used in bibliometric research
Title		
Title	1a	Identify the study is a bibliometric analysis.
	1b	Indicate the coverage period.
Abstract		
Abstract	2a	Provide an explicit statement of objective(s).
	2b	Specify the data sources.
	2c	Specify the coverage period.
	2d	Provide results for main outcomes.
	2e	Provide an overall interpretation of the results and implications.
Introduction		
Rationale	3	Describe the rationale for the study.
Objectives	4	Provide an explicit statement of objective(s).
Methods		
Data source	5a	Specific the database(s) or other data sources searched.
	5b	Describe the characteristics of the data source.
	5c	Specify the date when the search was conducted.
Eligibility criteria	6	Specify the inclusion and exclusion criteria, such as language, article types, and coverage period.
Search strategy	7	Specify the search strategy and keywords used.
Bibliometric indicators	8	Describe the bibliometric indicators used.
Analytical software	9	Specify the software package(s) used and the settings selected.
Results		
Search process	10	Describe the results of the search and selection processes, and use a flow diagram if necessary.
Bibliometric indicators	11	Describe the results of bibliometric indicators, including quantity, performance, and structural indicators.
Figures	12	Prepare figures with an adequate resolution for online and print readability.
Discussion		
Conclusions	13	Summarize key results with reference to study objective(s).
Limitations	14	Discuss any limitations and impact of potential bias.
Interpretation	15	Interpret the results in the context of background knowledge.
Other information		
Support	16	Describe the sources of financial or non-financial support and the role of funders or sponsors.
Conflicts of interest	17	Declare any competing interests of the author(s).
Data availability	18	Specify if data are publicly available and the route of access.

